

Experiments on Charge Reversal by Hydrogen and Hydroxyl Ions with insoluble Organic Acids and Amines and Reversal of the Charge of Hydrated Silica and Copper Oxide by Solutions of Salts.

BY

JNANENDRA NATH MUKHERJEE AND M. P. VENKATARAMA
IYER.

The influence of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions on the charge of colloidal particles is in some respects distinct from that of other ions. Firstly, their capacity to decrease the electrical charge of a colloidal surface of opposite sign is, in general, greater than that of other ions of the same valency. Secondly, reversal of the sign in the initial charge is to be met with more frequently in literature, when the colloid is brought in contact with acids or alkalis. Attention has been drawn to this peculiar behaviour of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions by Perrin (*J. Chim. Phys.*, 1904, 2, 601), Haber and Klemensiewicz (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, 47, 385) and others. One of us has reviewed the subject (*Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 44, 322) and pointed out the defects in the explanation of Perrin. Haber assumed that the surface, in virtue of its hydration, acts as a hydrogen and oxygen electrode. It

is well known that 'electrode' potentials are not identical with what has been termed by Freundlich as 'electrokinetic' potentials. The behaviour of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions was explained in the last mentioned paper from the point of view of the adsorption of ions and from considerations of neutralisation of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions in the fixed layer of water molecules on the surface, by hydroxyl and hydrogen ions respectively present in the solution (*loc. cit.*). Recently Bartell and Miller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1826; *ibid.*, 1923, 45, 1106) have made the very interesting observation that specially prepared charcoal, uncontaminated by any kind of inorganic salts, acids or alkalis when brought into contact with neutral solutions of salts, can give rise to acid or alkali. These authors (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 992) in explaining this so called hydrolytic adsorption points out that it is necessary to make assumptions similar to what has been suggested by Mukherjee.

Fajans (*Z. Physical. Chem.*, 1921, 97, 478) and Mukherjee (*Far. Soc. Disc.*, Oct., 1920) have pointed out that a strong adsorption of constituent ions by polar precipitates is to be expected (*vide* also Mukherjee and Roy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 173; Taylor, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 942). It is therefore of interest to see whether hydrogen and hydroxyl ions could not behave in a similar manner with insoluble acids and bases. For this purpose we undertook an examination of the effect of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions on the charge on the surfaces of particles of insoluble organic acids and amines. It would be also of interest to see which of the above two explanations will represent the facts better in such cases. In the course of this investigation, we have come across a fact of considerable interest regarding the theory of adsorption of ions. We have found that contrary to general

experience, in a number of cases, the charge on these particles as measured by the rate of electro-osmosis, is not affected by multivalent ions of opposite sign, though hydrogen and hydroxyl ions have a characteristic effect.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The variations in charge were measured by electro-osmotic experiments. The arrangement we used is that described in *Nature*, Dec. 2, 1922 (see also Mukherjee and B. C. Roy, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 480). The results recorded in this paper are of a semi-quantitative nature. Provided the movement of the air bubble is not too small, they are reproducible within 5 per cent.

In these experiments care was taken to see that the conditions were as far as possible identical. To minimise variations in temperature, the apparatus was immersed in a large bath of water. After each reading the substance in the bent portion of the U-tube was left at rest for some time.

The various sparingly soluble organic acids, which were used as diaphragms, were all recrystallised from absolute alcohol and washed thoroughly with conductivity water. The same sample was used for all the experiments. The substance was carefully washed with the electrolyte in question in steamed Jena-glass bottles and then kept in contact with the electrolyte for 24 hours, after which they were used for the electro-osmotic experiments.

TABLE I (A)*.
Sparingly soluble Acids.

Electrolyte : *Hydrochloric Acid.*

Concentration of electrolyte.	Benzoic acid.	Cinnamic acid.	Salicylic acid.	Boric acid.
Pure Water.	+1.4	-10.6	-8.1	-3.2
N/5000	+2.5	-9.5
N/2000	-2.7
N/1000	+4.5	-52	-0.4	...
N/500	+0.8	-1.3	-0.2	-0.5
N/100	0.0	-0.6	0.0	+1.25

TABLE I (B).

Sparingly soluble Acids.

Electrolyte : *Sodium Hydroxide.*

Concentration of electrolyte.	Benzoic acid.	Cinnamic acid.	Salicylic acid.	Boric acid.
Pure water value.	+1.4	-10.6	-8.1	-3.2
N/5000	+0.7	...	-11.3	...
N/2000	0.35	-9.0	...	-3.5
N/1000	...	-16.0	-13.7	...
N/500	0.0	-18.6	-12.4	-4.0
N/250	...	-21.9
N/100	-2.85	-18.6	-10.0	-3.35

* The electro-osmotic data given above represents the distance in *cms.* moved by the air bubble in 3 minutes. The sign in this and following tables indicates the sign of charge of the particles.

TABLE II (A).

*Sparingly soluble Amino acids.*Electrolyte: *Hydrochloric Acid.*

Concentration of electro-lyte.		Phenyl-glycine-o-carboxylic acid.	<i>m</i> -Amino-benzoic acid.
Pure water	-1.2	+0.35
<i>N</i> /5000	-0.9	+1.1
<i>N</i> /1000	+1.5	+4.5
<i>N</i> /500	+2.4	+6.6
<i>N</i> /250	+2.9	+8.9
<i>N</i> /100	+4.6	+12.0

TABLE II (B).

*Sparingly soluble Amino-acids.*Electrolyte: *Sodium Hydroxide.*

Concentration of electro-lyte,		Phenyl glycine-o-carboxylic acid.	<i>m</i> -Amino-benzoic acid.
<i>N</i> /5000	-1.45	-0.5
<i>N</i> /2000	-1.60	-1.85
<i>N</i> /500	-1.65	-1.85
<i>N</i> /250	-1.60	-5.60
<i>N</i> /100	-1.60	-8.50

TABLE III.

Sparingly soluble Amine and Ester.

Concentration of electrolyte.	<i>p</i> -Nitradiline.	Salol.
Pure water value ...	-15.70	-19.5
<i>Hydrochloric acid</i>		
<i>N</i> /2000 ...	-7.35	-12.7
<i>N</i> /500 ...	-2.70	-8.2
<i>N</i> /100 ...	+3.0	-5.1
<i>Sodium Hydroxide</i>		
<i>N</i> /2000 ...	-18.5	-30.0
<i>N</i> /500 ...	-18.0	-32.2
<i>N</i> /100 ...	-13.5	-30.0

TABLE IV.

Electrolyte: *Potassium Chloride*

Concentration of electrolyte.	Boric acid.	Benzoic acid.	Cinnamic acid	Salicylic acid.
Pure water ...	-3.2	+1.4	-8.0	-8.1
<i>N</i> /5000 ...	-1.9	+1.5	-8.3	-7.3
<i>N</i> /1000 ...	-1.9	...	-8.3	-7.3
<i>N</i> /500	+1.4	-8.2	-7.5
<i>N</i> /100 ...	-0.4	+1.3	-8.2	-8.0

TABLE V.
Electrolyte: *Barium Chloride.*

Concentration of electro-lyte.	Boric acid.	Cinnamic acid.
N/5000 	-1.95	-9.0
N/1000 	-1.90	-9.0
N/500 	-1.90	-9.5
N/100 	-0.70	-9.0

TABLE VI.
Cinnamic Acid and Aluminium Chloride.

Concentration of aluminium chloride.	Charge.
0	-8.0
N/2000 	-7.02
N/500 	-1.2
N/100 	0.0

Electro-osmotic experiments were also carried out with one inorganic insoluble acid and one insoluble base, namely hydrated silica and hydrated copper oxide. Only two electrolytes were used for experiments with silica as a number of electrolytes have been previously examined in this laboratory.

TABLE VII.
Hydrated Silica.

Concentration of electrolyte.	Aluminium chloride.	Aniline hydrochloride.
Pure water value.	-3.5	-3.5
N/10,000	...	-3.6
N/5,000	-4.6	-2.2
N/2,500	-4.2	-1.0
N/1,000	-2.4	-0.1
N/500	+0.5	+0.45
N/250	+1.6	+1.10
N/100	+1.5	+2.0

TABLE VIII.
Hydrated Copper Oxide.

Concentration of electrolyte.	Potassium sulphate.	Potassium chloride.	Sodium chloride.	Barium chloride.	Potassium nitrate.	Rubidium nitrate.
Pure water value	+2.757*	+4.4	+4.4	+4.4	+4.25	+4.25
N/5,000	+7.0	+11.6(?)	+13.7	...	+14.7	+14.6
N/1,000	+4.0	+16.5	+15.4	+14.9	+16.0	+12.7(?)
N/500	+2.6	+14.7	+14.3	+14.2	+13.6	+14.9
N/250	+1.5
N/100	-1.6	+13.3	+13.5	+13.6	+12.6	+13.1

* A different sample of the hydrated copper oxide was used for this experiment

DISCUSSION.

(A). *Adsorption of Constituent Ions.*

We shall consider in this section the influence of alkalis and acids on the charge on the insoluble organic acids, bases, and also on salol. From Tables I to III, it is evident that while benzoic and *m*-aminobenzoic acid are positively charged in contact with their own solution in pure water, the other acids investigated are negatively charged. It is to be noted that the positive charge on the particles is markedly increased or negative charge diminished by hydrochloric acid. In the case of boric and the amino acids we actually notice a reversal of charge. Boric acid behaves in one sense differently from the other acids. Alkali has little effect on its charge. It is probable that on account of the solubility of the acid and the greater strength of adsorption of the anion, the surface is nearly saturated with anions when the substance is in contact with its own saturated solution. In the other cases investigated, *e.g.*, salicylic and cinnamic acid in presence of hydrochloric acid, the charge tends to a zero value but up to the concentration used no reversal has been observed. In those cases where the particles have initially a small negative charge, it seems that a reversal can be observed whereas with cinnamic and salicylic acid there is no reversal of charge probably on account of the initial high negative charge on the surface. We could not use higher concentrations of acid, as the evolution of gases on account of electrolysis produces a serious source of error in our measurements. In fact, the change in volume consequent on evolution of gases is already a source of error at the higher concentrations for which measurements are given in the tables. Further it should be noted that the figures given above can give us no

definite information regarding the relative intensities of the adsorption by these substances as the size of the capillary passages, the actual potential drop and the potential gradient are not all identical. The values, however, give us a qualitative idea of the general nature of the variations.

Regarding the influence of the hydroxyl ion on the charge on these surfaces, it is noticed that in all these cases, with two exceptions, the particles become more negatively charged. In the alkaline solutions there are evidently the anions of these acids, *i.e.*, benzoate, cinnamate, salicylate, etc., and the results obtained show that there is a strong tendency towards the adsorption of these constituent ions. Even in this case, we notice that at a higher concentration there is a slight but much less marked diminution of the negative charge which again points to the electrical adsorption of the cation.

In the case of the two amino acids which are amphoteric, we notice a greater tendency on their part to get positively charged. It is also to be observed that the increase in the negative charge on the addition of alkali is not so great as for the other acids. The presence of amino group seems to increase the adsorption of the hydrogen ions and decrease that of the anion or hydroxyl ions.

To sum up, we notice :

(a) For the acids, a strong adsorption of constituent ions.

(b) In the contact with saturated solution of the acids, two of them (benzoic acid and *m*-aminobenzoic acid) are positively charged. The rest are negatively charged. It seems that of the constituent ions, in some cases, the hydrogen and in other case the anion (or hydroxylion) is more strongly adsorbed.

(c) At higher concentrations the adsorption of the ion with a charge of opposite sign to that carried by the surface becomes more pronounced.

(d) The amino acids take up a positive charge more easily than the others implying that the amino groups on the surface react with hydrogen ions in solution and lead to the adsorption of the latter. The strength of the adsorption of the hydrogen ions is also indicated by the fact that even at fairly high concentrations, the positive charge does not decrease on account of the anion adsorption. Hydrogen ions are thus more strongly adsorbed than the anion (hydroxyl ions).

(e) It is rather surprising that both *p*-nitraniline and salol carry a negative charge in contact with pure water, indicating strong adsorption of the hydroxyl ions. A reversal of charge has not been observed for salol up to a concentration of *N*/100 hydrochloric acid. The strong adsorption of the hydroxyl ions is also indicated by the very large increase in the negative charge in the presence of sodium hydroxide. In both these cases we have to conclude that the hydroxyl ions (of the anion of the acid) are more strongly adsorbed than the hydrogen ions.

From the above, it appears that the constitution of the acid has a decided influence on the intensity of adsorption of hydrogen ions and of the anion of the acid, but it is also to be noted that considerations of constitution alone cannot give us an indication of the strength of adsorption of the ions. This is what is to be expected if the adsorption of the constituent ions lead to the growth of the crystal in conformity with its structure. Though the conditions in the interface are not the same as those inside the crystal, yet the energy change associated with the change in hydration, should also be taken into account.

We have stated in the introduction that the strong adsorption of the hydrogen ions may be referred either to the adsorption of a constituent ion or to the neutralisation of the hydroxyl ions in the fixed layer of adsorbed water molecules by the hydrogen ions in the solution. The fact that the substances in contact with their saturated solutions are either positively or negatively charged according to their nature points definitely to the primary and preferential adsorption of one of the ions (compare Mukherjee, *Phil. Mag.*, *loc. cit.* p. 330).

(B). *Effect of Solutions of Salts on the Charge of sparingly Soluble Acids.*

It is well known that the adsorption of constituent ions is much more intense than that of other ions, even if they carry a charge of opposite sign to that of the surface. From Tables IV, V and VI we find that neutral electrolytes have very little effect on the charge. In the case of boric acid, we find that both potassium chloride and barium chloride bring down the charge to nearly zero at a concentration of $N/100$; whereas in the case of cinnamic, salicylic and benzoic acids, neutral electrolytes have practically no effect on the charge. On comparing the effect of aluminium chloride with that of hydrochloric acid on cinnamic acid, we find that there is very little difference between the two sets of values. Considering that hydrogen ions are present in the solution on account of hydrolysis, aluminium ions do not seem to have much effect. The observation that potassium and barium chloride and probably aluminium chloride have very little effect on some of the acids is rather unusual. We are not aware of similar observations. The great difference in the adsorption between the ions of neutral electrolytes, and the constituent ions, *points to the*

conclusion that the latter are primarily adsorbed by chemical forces and are not electrically adsorbed in a hydrated state. These observations also point to the conclusion that the surface is strongly hydrated, and consequently the electrical adsorption as defined by one of us is very weak. It has been pointed out by one of us, (*Phil. Mag., loc. cit.*) that adsorption of hydrogen ions or hydroxyl ions from the solution in a dehydrated state cannot be distinguished from the neutralisation by these ions of the hydroxyl or hydrogen ions respectively present in the primarily adsorbed layer resulting from the dissociation of water molecules. The weakness of the adsorption of other oppositely charged ions and the strong effect of hydrogen ions point to the existence of this type of neutralisation. Thus we are inclined to believe that in addition to a strong adsorption of constituent ions, we are dealing with the neutralisation of hydroxyl and hydrogen ions present in the primary layer, by hydrogen and hydroxyl ions respectively in the solution and resulting in the formation of water molecules.

The observation that the charge of boric acid is not at all affected by alkali can be explained from this point of view if we assume that boric acid being a relatively stronger acid, the hydroxyl ion concentration is smaller, and hence the neutralising effect is almost absent. As stated before, the surface must be assumed to be saturated with anions at low concentration.*

(C). *Inorganic Acids and Bases.*

It has been observed by Krishnamurti* in this laboratory that up to a concentration of $N/100$, hydrochloric acid does not reverse the charge of hydrated silica. He could not also observe a reversal in the charge with

* Unpublished work.

barium chloride. As silica is negatively charged in contact with water it was expected that trivalent ions may reverse the charge. Mukherjee and B. C. Roy (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 476) observed that in presence of aniline hydrochloride the negatively charged sols of mastic, gamboge, etc., become positively charged. It will be seen from Table VII that both aluminium chloride and aniline hydrochloride produce a reversal in the charge of silica. The absence of a reversal with acids is probably connected with the fact that the hydrogen ion is not a constituent ion of the solid phase as it is in the case of the organic acids. The silicic acid molecules probably exist on the surface only and there in a hydrated state. The initial rise in the charge followed by a reversal observed with aluminium chloride is of considerable theoretical interest as this form of the curve is difficult to explain from the point of view of the independent adsorption of cations and anions by a negatively charged surface (Mukherjee, *Phil. Mag.*, *loc. cit.* p. 343).

The influence of neutral electrolytes on copper hydroxide is in contrast to their effect on the organic acids or on silica. These results have an important bearing on the nature of the exchange of ions between those in the double layer and those in the solution. It will be seen from Table VIII that sulphate ions can reverse the charge and we attribute this property to its being divalent. The ions in the primary layer must be assumed to be univalent. They are probably cupric ions with a 'fixed' hydroxyl ion forming univalent units. What is more interesting to observe is that all the other five electrolytes practically show the same behaviour and the positive charge increases in each case to a maximum and then decreases. For the chlorides *the rate of flow at the same normal concentration is practically independent of the cation.* The increase in the charge cannot be

due to the adsorption of cations, as otherwise differences between the effect of different cations were sure to have been observed. The increase in the charge probably indicates that the anion of the electrolyte penetrates the double layer, and a redistribution of ions takes place, and a number of hydroxyl ions are displaced from the double layer and that a larger number of positively charged copper ions remain 'uncovered' than before. The ions in the primary layer must be in equilibrium with those in the mobile sheet. The relative numbers of hydroxyl ions and other anions in the mobile sheet are mainly determined by their relative concentrations in the solution. There being now a considerable number of anions (other than hydroxyl) in the mobile sheet, the anions in the primary layer which cover the 'fixed' cupric ions will in part consist of the anions of the electrolyte. On account of the weaker adsorbability of chloride or nitrate ion as compared with that of hydroxyl ions there will remain a larger number of free positive charges in the primary layer.

Summary and Conclusion.

(1) Acids and alkalis have a marked effect on the charge on the surface of particles of insoluble organic acids.

(2) Insoluble organic acids (including amino acids) show a strong adsorption of the constituent ions, and one of the constituent ions is in general more strongly adsorbed than the other.

(3) Neutral electrolytes, *e.g.*, potassium chloride or barium chloride have little effect on the charge of the sparingly soluble acids.

(4) It has been shown that besides a strong adsorption of constituent ions we have evidence of the adsorption of

hydrogen and hydroxyl ions in a dehydrated state. This type of adsorption probably consists in part in the neutralisation of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions in the primary layer (which are formed by the dissociation of fixed water molecules) by hydroxyl and hydrogen ions respectively in the solution.

(5) Presence of the amino group increases the adsorbability of hydrogen ions.

(6) Aniline hydrochloride and aluminium chloride reverse the charge of silica. With aluminium chloride there is an increase in the negative charge at low concentrations and then a decrease followed by a reversal.

(7) Sulphate ions reverse the charge of copper oxide. No reversal has been observed with chloride and nitrate. Neutral electrolytes increase the positive charge of copper hydroxide. The effect depends on the anion and is independent of the nature of the cation (potassium, sodium, barium). The importance of this observation has been pointed out.